

Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to determine research mapping around the Net Operating Margin (NOM) ratio in Sharia Banking using a mix-method approach, namely a VOSviewer bibliometric study and a Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the NOM ratio; (2) mapping the results of VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the NOM ratio based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map research topics around the NOM ratio using a Library Research study. The research results show that: (1) based on mapping the distribution of journal publications, there are 18 journal publications around the NOM ratio; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the NOM ratio are divided into 3 clusters and 58 topic items; (3) based on mapping Library Research studies, there are 4 topics regarding the influence of the NOM ratio and 8 topics regarding the determinants of the NOM ratio. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the NOM ratio in Sharia Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Net Operating Margin (NOM); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Banking

Introduction

Net Operating Margin (NOM) ratio in banking has experienced significant development over the last few years. One of the factors influencing the development of the use of the NOM ratio is the increasing competition in the banking industry. This increasingly fierce competition encourages banks to pay more attention to operational efficiency in an effort to maintain and increase profits. Therefore, the NOM ratio is increasingly being used by banks as a tool to measure and monitor their operational efficiency. Apart from that, developments in technology and automation also have an impact on the use of the NOM ratio. Technological developments have helped banks increase operational efficiency and minimize operational costs. By using technology, banks can carry out business processes more quickly and efficiently, which has a positive impact on the NOM ratio because more and more banks are able to generate greater profits with smaller assets.

Increasingly stringent regulations and supervision are also other factors that influence the use of the NOM ratio. Banks are required to meet increasingly stringent regulations and supervision requirements, including the use of financial ratios as performance indicators. Therefore, more and more banks are using the NOM ratio as an indicator of their performance. In the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, the NOM ratio has become increasingly important as a tool for measuring bank operational efficiency during the pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has affected banking performance throughout the world, including Indonesia. Banks are required to face pressure in terms of improving operational efficiency and maintaining profits. The NOM ratio is an important tool in helping banks to measure their operational efficiency and make strategic decisions in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic. In order to maximize the use of the NOM ratio, banks must pay attention to several things. First, banks must understand the meaning and how to calculate the NOM ratio correctly. Second, banks must identify the factors that influence the NOM ratio and take appropriate actions to improve their operational efficiency. Third, banks should compare their NOM ratio with competing banks to find out their position in

the banking industry. By paying attention to these things, banks can maximize the use of the NOM ratio to increase operational efficiency and maintain their profits.

Net Operating Margin (NOM) is a financial ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating revenue from its main business operations. In the banking context, NOM measures a bank's ability to generate operational income (such as interest and fee-based income) after deducting operational costs (such as employee salaries, rental costs and administrative costs). NOM is calculated by dividing net operating income (Net operating income) by total assets. The higher the NOM, the more efficient the bank is in generating income from its business operations, and the more likely the bank is to have good profitability. However, keep in mind that the NOM does not provide an overview of the quality of a bank's assets or the credit risks it faces. Therefore, it is important to evaluate other financial ratios to get a more complete picture of a bank's financial condition.

Bibliometric studies are research method that examines the quantity and quality of scientific or academic publications in a particular field using bibliographic and statistical data. Bibliometric studies involve the collection, analysis, and interpretation of bibliographic data, including counting the number of publications, citations, and collaborations between researchers in the field under study. The main aim of a bibliometric study is to measure the impact and productivity of research in a particular field, as well as to identify emerging publication trends and patterns. In bibliometric studies, frequently used metrics are number of publications, number of citations, journal impact factor and Hirsch index. Bibliometric studies can be conducted in a variety of disciplines, including science, engineering, social sciences, and humanities. This method can provide important information for researchers, journal publishers, libraries and policy-making institutions in determining appropriate research policies and publication strategies.

VOSviewer is bibliometric data analysis and visualization software developed by Nees Jan van Eck and Ludo Waltman of the Technical University of Delft, the Netherlands. This software is used to analyze and visualize bibliometric data, such as citation networks, keywords, or collaboration between authors. VOSviewer allows users to import bibliometric data from various sources, such as the Web of Science or Scopus databases, and perform quantitative and qualitative analysis of the data. Quantitative analysis includes calculating citation frequency, keyword frequency, and relationships between keywords, while qualitative analysis includes document classification and network analysis. Once the analysis is complete, VOSviewer allows users to visualize bibliometric data in a variety of formats, including network maps, hierarchical trees, or 3D graphs. The visualizations produced by VOSviewer can help users to understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data, as well as to identify linkages and relationships between documents, keywords, or authors. VOSviewer is open source software that is free to use and has been used widely in various bibliometric research in various fields of science.

Studies Library Research is research methods used to review and analyze literature that has been published in a particular field of science or topic. The goal is to collect, evaluate, and synthesize knowledge and findings that have been developed by previous researchers in the field. Library Research studies are carried out by collecting, reading and identifying articles, books, journals or other documents that are relevant to the research topic you want to review. After that, data from the literature is analyzed and synthesized to provide a comprehensive picture of the research topic. Library Research studies are often used in academic and scientific research to gain a deeper understanding of a particular topic, as well as to identify knowledge gaps or unanswered research questions. Library Research studies can also provide a basis for formulating hypotheses or theoretical frameworks in research. One of the advantages of a Library Research study is that it can provide a more comprehensive and representative picture of the research topic, because it is based on data that has been published and is academically recognized. However, Library

Research studies also have weaknesses, such as the risk of selection bias and difficulty in finding relevant and up-to-date literature.

Research on the NOM ratio in banking continues to develop along with the increasing importance of this ratio as a performance indicator in the banking industry. Several recent studies have been conducted to dig deeper into the factors that influence the NOM ratio and its impact on banking performance. First, one study identified that information technology (IT) has a positive influence on the NOM ratio. They concluded that banks that adopt more information technology can improve operational efficiency and reduce operational costs, thereby increasing the NOM ratio and overall financial performance. Second, other research in South Korea found that bank size, asset quality and liquidity had a significant effect on the NOM ratio. They suggest that banks should pay attention to these factors to improve operational efficiency and maintain their profits. Third, other research shows that external factors such as regulation and competition in the banking industry also influence the NOM ratio. They found that banks operating in more competitive markets had lower NOM ratios compared to banks operating in less competitive markets. These studies show that internal and external factors have a significant influence on the NOM ratio in banking. Therefore, banks must pay attention to these factors in an effort to increase operational efficiency and maintain their profits. Fourth, research also shows that the NOM ratio can be used as a tool to compare banking performance between banks, which found that the NOM ratio can be used as a tool to compare banking performance between banks of different sizes. They suggest that the NOM ratio can be used as a criterion in selecting banks that have good financial performance. Overall, research on the NOM ratio in banking continues to develop and shows that this ratio has a significant influence on bank financial performance. Therefore, banks must pay attention to the NOM ratio as a tool to measure operational efficiency and maintain their profits in the competition in the banking industry.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around NOM in Sharia Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding NOM. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research NOM. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the NOM ratio in Sharia Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Net Operating Margin (NOM). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about NOM in Sharia Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Net Operating Margin " and " NOM" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around NOM using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on

financing, object, ratio, research, rest, sample, significant effect/negative effect/on net operating margin, value.

- Cluster 3, consists of 14 topic items, namely: sharia commercial banks, buses, development, Indonesia, quantitative, management, negative effects, sharia banking, r square, secondary data, sharia commercial banks, type, variables.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Effect of Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Sharia Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 4 influences of NOM on Sharia Banking, namely:

First, efficiency. Efficiency in banking refers to how efficiently a bank manages its operational costs. There is a positive relationship between NOM and efficiency in banking. The higher the NOM ratio, the more likely the bank is to generate sufficient profits to cover operational costs and improve operational efficiency. In this case, banks can use the remaining income to increase investment in technology and infrastructure to improve operational efficiency. Additionally, the more efficient a bank is in managing its operational costs, the higher the NOM ratio is likely to be. In this case, banks can minimize their operational costs, thereby increasing operating profits and possibly resulting in a higher NOM ratio. However, it is important to remember that the relationship between NOM and bank efficiency is not a simple cause-and-effect relationship. There are many other factors that can influence banking performance, such as asset quality, market risk, and regulatory policies. Therefore, it is important for banks to pay attention to and monitor all of these factors in order to produce a good NOM ratio and increase operational efficiency in a sustainable manner.

Second, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. FDR is a ratio that measures the size of the loan provided by the bank against the funds collected from customers. The influence of NOM on FDR in banking can vary depending on the banking policy in question. However, in general, the higher the NOM ratio, the more likely a bank is to have more funds available to make loans and increase FDR. This is because the higher the NOM ratio, the greater the possibility for the bank to have sufficient profits to cover operational costs and increase internal funding. In this case, banks can use the remaining income to increase lending and increase FDR. However, keep in mind that the influence of NOM on FDR can be influenced by other factors such as credit risk and liquidity risk. Banking policies that prioritize risk control rather than increasing lending can affect FDR even though the NOM ratio is high. Therefore, it is important for banks to achieve a balance between generating profits and controlling risks, so as to increase FDR and improve overall banking health.

Third, Return On Assets/ROA. In banking, a high level of NOM indicates that the company is able to generate greater profits from its core business operations. Conversely, if NOM is low, this indicates that the company's operating costs are too high or the company's operating income is too low. At the same time, ROA shows how effective the company is in utilizing all the assets it owns to generate profits. If ROA is high, this shows that the company is able to generate greater profits from the assets it owns. Conversely, if ROA is low, this indicates that the company is less efficient in utilizing its assets to generate profits. In relation to banking, NOM and ROA can influence each other. If NOM increases, this can increase company profits and ultimately increase ROA. However, if the company's operating costs increase faster than operating income, this will reduce NOM and ultimately reduce ROA. Therefore, banks need to ensure that their operational costs remain under control and maximize their operational income in order to increase NOM and ROA simultaneously.

Fourth, Return On Equity /ROE. ROE is a ratio that measures the efficiency of using banking capital in generating profits. The influence of NOM on ROE in banking is very important. The higher the NOM ratio, the more likely a bank is to generate sufficient profits to provide greater returns to shareholders and improve its ROE. This is because the higher the NOM ratio, the greater the bank's possibility of

generating sufficient profits to strengthen capital and provide greater returns to shareholders. In this case, the bank can increase its ROE and provide higher returns to shareholders. However, keep in mind that the influence of NOM on ROE can also be influenced by other factors such as capital management, credit risk and market risk. Banking policies that prioritize controlling risk rather than increasing profits can affect ROE even though the NOM ratio is high. Therefore, it is important for banks to achieve a balance between generating profits and controlling risks, so as to increase ROE and provide higher returns to shareholders. Banks must also pay attention to other factors such as asset quality, liquidity and regulatory compliance to ensure their performance is at a healthy and sustainable level.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research Study regarding the Determinant Variables of Net Operating Margin (NOM) in Sharia Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 8 determinant variables for NOM in Sharia Banking, namely:

First, productive assets. Productive assets or loan portfolios are the main source of income for banks. In this case, the greater the productive assets owned by the bank, the greater the interest income generated by the bank. NOM is a financial ratio that measures a bank's ability to generate profits from the bank's main operations, namely lending and fund raising activities. The higher the NOM ratio, the greater the bank's ability to generate profits from main operations. In relation to the influence of productive assets on NOM in banking, it can be concluded that the greater the productive assets owned by a bank, the greater the bank's ability to generate interest income and generate profits from main operations, so that the bank's NOM ratio can increase. However, this also depends on the interest rate given by the bank to its customers and the level of bank operational costs. If the interest rate provided by the bank is lower than the level of bank operational costs, then the bank's NOM ratio may decrease even though the bank's productive assets are increasing. Therefore, banks need to manage productive assets well in order to increase the NOM ratio. Apart from that, banks also need to pay attention to the interest rates given to their customers and manage operational costs to remain efficient.

Second, Financing to Deposit Ratio /FDR. FDR and NOM are two main indicators in measuring banking financial performance. FDR measures the proportion of loans provided by banks compared to funds received from deposits, while NOM measures a bank's operational efficiency in generating income from its business activities. The influence of FDR on NOM in banking can vary depending on market conditions and the bank's business strategy. In general, the higher the FDR, the higher the credit risk taken by banks because they have to borrow more funds to finance the loan. However, if banks manage to minimize their credit risks and generate sufficient income from their business activities, they can still achieve good operating margins despite high FDR. On the other hand, if banks take on higher risks by providing more loans than funds received from deposits, they may have difficulty meeting repayment obligations and experience a decline in operating margins. Additionally, if banks focus too much on obtaining funding from overseas or through more expensive resources, this could impact their operating margins due to higher funding costs. In conclusion, the influence of FDR on NOM in banking can vary depending on factors such as credit risk management, funding strategy, and operational efficiency. It is important for banks to consider these factors in managing their business to achieve optimal operating margins and long-term financial stability.

Third, Non Performing Financing /NPF. NPF refers to credit or financing that is not repaid by customers and exceeds a certain time limit. Meanwhile, NOM is a financial ratio that measures a bank's ability to generate profits from its operations after considering operational costs. A high NPF can have a negative impact on banking NOM, because banks have to bear the burden of losses due to bad credit. This can reduce bank profitability and the bank's ability to generate profits from its

operations. Apart from that, banks also have to increase loss reserves to cover the risk of bad credit, so that bank operational costs increase. In other words, the higher the NPF, the lower the bank's NOM. Therefore, banks need to manage credit risk well and carry out appropriate risk management to reduce the risk of bad credit. In this case, banks can improve the quality of their credit portfolio and diversify risks by expanding the customer base and types of businesses served. This can help reduce the risk of bad credit and increase bank profitability.

Fourth, financing is problematic. Non-performing financing/NPLs can have a significant impact on NOM in banking. NOM is the ratio between a bank's net operating income and total assets, which measures a bank's ability to generate income from its operational activities. When the number of Non-Performing Loans increases, banks tend to experience a decrease in income, because they have to spend more funds to handle these bad loans. Banks must also maintain higher reserves to overcome the risk of Non-Performing Financing, which can reduce their net profits. In addition, Problematic Financing can affect the bank's reputation and customer trust, which can reduce investment returns and increase bank funding costs. This can reduce the bank's ability to generate revenue and generate profits. Thus, Problematic Financing can affect NOM in banks by reducing operational income and increasing funding costs. Therefore, good credit risk management and appropriate preventive measures are essential for banks to minimize the negative impact of Non-Performing Financing on their financial performance.

Fifth, allowance for losses on productive assets. Allowance for productive asset losses (PPAP) is an accounting obligation that must be made by banks to anticipate losses in their credit portfolio. PPAP affects NOM because PPAP reduces net interest income and net banking profits. In practice, PPAP is influenced by economic conditions and the level of credit risk. When economic conditions are bad or credit risk increases, banks will increase the PPAP level to anticipate future losses. In this case, PPAP can reduce net interest income and banking net profit, thereby reducing NOM. However, on the other hand, PPAP can also improve the quality of banking assets and reduce credit risk, which in the end can improve the long-term performance of banks and make them more stable. In this case, PPAP can increase market confidence in banks, which in turn can improve their financial performance and strengthen NOM. Overall, the effect of PPAP on NOM depends on how much PPAP is made by banks and economic conditions and the level of credit risk in the market. However, in general, if the PPAP is made reasonably and proportional to credit risk, then the PPAP can help strengthen banking financial performance in the long term, although there may be a temporary impact on NOM in the short term.

Sixth, Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing. Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing are two types of sharia financing that are generally implemented by sharia banking. Mudharabah financing is financing carried out between banks and customers with a profit sharing scheme, while Musyarakah financing is financing with a collaboration scheme between banks and customers in a project or business. The influence of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on NOM in sharia banking varies depending on how much use of these two types of financing is in the banking portfolio. On the one hand, Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing tend to have higher margins than conventional financing because they are based on profit sharing or mutual profits. So, if banks succeed in managing risks well and maximizing profits in profit sharing schemes, then this can increase NOM. However, on the other hand, Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing tends to have higher risks than conventional financing due to the risks of the business or project being financed. If the business or project fails, banking will experience greater losses than conventional financing. This may lead to a decrease in NOM if the resulting losses are significant. Apart from that, sharia banking also needs to manage sharia risks in Mudharabah and Musyarakah Financing, such as the risk of compliance with sharia principles, operational risk and reputation risk. Overall, the influence of Mudharabah and Musyarakah Financing on NOM in sharia banking is very

dependent on the extent to which these two types of financing are used in the banking portfolio, the bank's ability to manage the related risks, and market conditions and existing competition. If banks succeed in managing risks well and maximizing potential profits from Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing, then this can increase NOM in the long term.

Seventh, Qardh loans. The influence of Qardh loans on NOM in banking can be understood by looking at how Qardh loans are obtained and managed by banks. Qardh loans are a form of interest-free loans provided by banks to customers who need funds for certain purposes, such as business funding or investment. In this case, the effect of Qardh loans on NOM in banks can vary depending on how banks manage these loans. In the case of Qardh loans, banks usually lend funds from halal sources, such as deposits or third party funds, so that there are no interest costs that must be paid by the customer. In this case, the effect of Qardh loans on NOM in banking depends on how banks manage their operational costs. If banks are able to manage their operational costs well, then Qardh loans can increase banking revenues and net profit margins (NOM). On the other hand, if banking operational costs are high, then the effect of Qardh loans on NOM can be insignificant or even negative. In this case, banks also need to consider the credit risks associated with Qardh loans, such as credit risk, liquidity risk and operational risk. If banks are able to manage this risk well, then the effect of Qardh loans on NOM can be positive. In conclusion, the effect of Qardh loans on NOM in banks depends on how banks manage their operational costs and credit risk. If banks are able to manage both well, then Qardh loans can increase banking revenues and net profit margins. However, if not, then the effect can be insignificant or even negative.

Eighth, Murabahah receivables. Murabahah receivables are a form of sharia financing provided by banks to their customers under a goods buying and selling scheme. In this case, the bank buys goods that customers want and resells them with a price markup. The customer pays the price of the goods in pre-agreed installments. The influence of Murabahah Receivables on NOM in banking can vary, depending on the factors that influence it. In general, Murabahah Receivables can make a significant contribution to banking revenues and, therefore, can increase NOM. However, the influence of Murabahah Receivables on NOM can also be influenced by other factors such as operational costs, interest rates, credit risk and other macroeconomic factors. Operational costs can increase if the bank has to buy goods that customers want and resell them. The interest rate can also affect bank profits from Murabahah Receivables, because the markup on the price of resold goods can be calculated based on the prevailing interest rates. Apart from that, credit risk is also an important factor in determining the effect of Murabahah Receivables on NOM. If the bank cannot obtain payments from customers on time, the bank may experience losses and affect the NOM. In conclusion, the influence of Murabahah Receivables on NOM in banking can vary depending on the factors that influence it, such as operational costs, interest rates, credit risk, and other macroeconomic factors. However, in general, Murabahah Receivables can make a positive contribution to banking income and therefore, can increase NOM.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on mapping the number of research publications around the ratio Net Operating Margin (NOM) in Sharia Banking for the period 20-17 to 2022 which comes from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 18 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the NOM ratio in Sharia Banking are divided into 3 clusters and 58 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 23 topics, cluster 2 consists of 2 1 topics, and cluster 3 consists of 1 4 topics. Third, based on mapping studies Library Research, there are 4 topics related to the influence of the NOM ratio on Sharia Banking, namely: efficiency, Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR), Return On Assets

(ROA), Return On Equity (ROE). And there are 8 topics related to the determinants of the NOM ratio in Sharia Banking, namely: productive assets, Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR), Non Performing Financing (NPF), problem financing, allowance for productive asset losses, Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing, Qardh, and Murabahah receivables.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital

Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>

Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/idejeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>

- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>